

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTIMALARIALS. PART VI. SYNTHESIS
OF SOME NEW 1:2-DIHYDRO-1:3:5-TRIAZINES

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Sixteen 4:6-diamino-1-aryl-2-methyl-2-substituted aminomethyl-1:2-dihydro-1:3:5-triazine hydrochlorides have been prepared with a view to testing their antimalarial activity.

In view of the encouraging antimalarial activity shown by 4:6-diamino-1-(*p*-anisyl)-2-methyl-2-(β -hydroxybutyl)-1:2-dihydro-1:3:5-triazine hydrochloride and 4:6-diamino-1-(*p*-phenetyl)-2-methyl-2-(β -hydroxybutyl)-1:2-dihydro-1:3:5-triazine hydrochloride (Sen and Singh, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 260), which were found to be four and fourteen times respectively more active than quinine, when tested against *P. gallinaceum* infection in chicken, prompted us to synthesise dihydrotriazine derivatives (I) in which the 2-(β -hydroxybutyl) grouping had been replaced by different aminomethyl groups, with the object of studying the variation of activity with the alteration in the basicity of the molecule.

[I : R' = substituted amino group]

The dihydrotriazine hydrochlorides were prepared by the condensation of *p*-anisyl-, *p*-phenetyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *p*-bromophenyl-, *p*-iodophenyl-, and 3-chloro-4-bromophenyl-biguanide hydrochlorides with diethylaminoacetone, piperidinoacetone, and morpholinoacetone by the method of Modest and Levine (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 14).

The dihydrotriazines have been characterised through their picrates and distinguished from the corresponding arylbiguanides by the non-formation of a coloured complex with cuprammonium sulphate, a test for biguanide type of grouping that involves chelation at N² and N⁴.

The antimalarial activities of these compounds are being evaluated at the Malaria Institute of India, Delhi.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Anisyl-, *p*-phenetyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *p*-bromophenyl-, *p*-iodophenyl- and 3-chloro-4-bromophenyl-biguanide hydrochlorides were prepared from the corresponding aniline hydrochlorides (0.1M) and dicyandiamide (0.1M) by the general procedure described by King and Tonkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 1063).

N: *N*-Diethylaminoacetone and *N*-piperidinoacetone were prepared according to the methods of Stoermer and Dzimski (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2226) and Stoermer and Burkert (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1250) respectively.

N-Morpholinoacetone was prepared in the same way, b.p. 196-98°, yield 83%. (Found: N, 9.74. C₇H₁₃O₂N requires N, 9.79%).

Morpholinoacetoxime was prepared from morpholinoacetone and hydroxylamine in the usual way, m.p. 98-99°. (Found: N, 17.63. C₇H₁₄O₂N₂ requires N, 17.72%).

1 : 2-Dihydro-1 : 3 : 5-triazine Hydrochlorides.—A mixture of arylbiguanide hydrochloride (0.1M) and the ketone (0.15M) in absolute ethanol (80 c.c.) was refluxed with stirring on a water bath. The condensation was complete after 18-20 hours, when the reaction mixture no longer gave a coloured precipitate with cuprammonium sulphate. The reaction mixture was then cooled in ice when crystals separated. These were filtered, washed, and recrystallised from 50% ethanol.

Picrates.—Crystalline picrates of the dihydrotriazines were readily obtained on mixing the hot saturated 50% ethanolic solutions of picric acid and the respective dihydrotriazine. The dihydrotriazine hydrochlorides and their picrates are listed together in Table I.

TABLE I
(Vide formula)

R.	Triazines.			Picrates.				
	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.
R' = N,N-Diethylamino.								
p-OMe	226°	63%	23.57	23.70	179°	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₉	22.96	23.04
p-OEt	204°	71	22.86	22.80	184°	C ₂₂ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₉	22.41	22.46
p-Me	248°	56	24.89	25.10	184°	C ₂₇ H ₃₉ O ₃ N ₉	23.67	23.73
p-Cl	240°	67	23.32	23.40	192°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ Cl	22.78	22.85
R' = N-Piperidino.								
p-OMe	228°	61	22.98	23.11	187°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₉	22.51	22.54
p-OEt	211°	72	21.88	22.08	180°	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ O ₃ N ₉	21.79	21.99
p-Me	243°	79	23.92	23.97	173°	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₉	23.06	23.21
p-Cl	237°	83	22.55	22.63	190°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ Cl	22.32	22.36
p-Br	247°	73	20.20	20.22	188°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ Br	20.68	20.73
p-I	245°	58	18.05	18.17	182°	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ I	19.20	19.24
3-Cl-4-Br	223°	69	18.66	18.67	168°	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₉ ClBr	19.57	19.62
R' = N-Morpholino.								
p-OMe	227°	67	18.24	18.30	184°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉	22.55	22.62
p-OEt	211°	72	22.13	22.19	176°	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₉	21.88	22.07
p-Me	238°	80	24.02	24.10	183°	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₉	23.21	23.29
p-Cl	231°	77	22.68	22.77	191°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ Cl	22.39	22.44
p-Br	218°	73	20.31	20.32	187°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₉ Br	20.72	20.79